

High-Performance Quantum Simulation with Adaptive Circuit Knitting

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Abstract—Simulating quantum systems is a promising application for quantum computing. However, quantum computers of sufficient scale and quality to study scientifically interesting systems beyond the limit of classical computers do not yet exist. It will be necessary in the near term to efficiently partition and distribute quantum workloads in an HPC environment. Circuit knitting provides a path to simulating large systems on quantum devices of a limited size by reconstructing observables from smaller sub-circuits, but this reconstruction comes at an exponential cost. We present an adaptive circuit knitting method which finds efficient partitions of quantum circuits by discovering regions of minimal entanglement between subsystems. We apply this method to simulating the dynamics of strongly-disordered quantum spin chains, and show reductions in the cost of circuit knitting of one to two orders of magnitude.

Index Terms—quantum computing, circuit knitting, tensor networks, HPC, QPU

I. INTRODUCTION

Quantum computers have the potential to provide exponential speedups compared to their classical counterparts for a range of applications including simulating quantum systems, machine learning on quantum data, and factorization. Instead of replacing classical computers as stand-alone processors, however, quantum computers can be better understood as accelerators or co-processors that can efficiently carry out specialized tasks within an HPC framework (Figure 1). Hybrid quantum-classical algorithms and frameworks will be crucial not only in the near term—the noisy intermediate-scale quantum or NISQ era—but also for future fault-tolerance, as error-correction schemes will rely heavily on classical HPC. In either case, to scale quantum computers and achieve true high-performance quantum simulation, methods to efficiently partition and distribute quantum tasks are necessary.

Efficiently partitioning quantum systems has a rich history in quantum science [1]–[3]. In recent years, circuit knitting has emerged as a promising method to partition quantum circuits, the primary goal being to enable simulating large circuits on devices available today which are limited to ~ 100 qubits [4], [5]. In circuit knitting, a measured observable is reconstructed by sampling sub-circuits of the original circuit multiple times. However, when cutting gates this reconstruction comes at an exponential cost in the number of samples that depends on the identity and number of gates that are cut [5]. While recent efforts have focused on reducing this exponential overhead

Fig. 1. Integration of distributed quantum and classical supercomputing for high-performance quantum simulation.

[6]–[8], further work is necessary to demonstrate the practical advantage of circuit knitting.

In this work, we present a method called *adaptive circuit knitting* which decreases sampling overhead by cutting in locations that minimize entanglement between partitions. In the following, we present the method and demonstrate its application simulating the dynamics of quantum spin chains.

II. METHOD: ADAPTIVE CIRCUIT KNITTING

Our adaptive circuit knitting method draws from tensor network (TN) approaches developed in the quantum physics and quantum chemistry communities [1], [2]. Tensor networks represent quantum states in a compressed form, and can provide structure to characterize entanglement patterns. In the context of quantum circuits, a TN can be efficiently expressed as circuit of linear depth as was shown by Lin et. al [9] for matrix product states (MPS), a type of TN widely used to study 1D quantum systems. Combining the structure of TNs with linear depth quantum circuits is the basis for our method.

Figure 2 provides a schematic for the adaptive circuit knitting method. We begin with a TN representation of a quantum state (in the figure, an MPS for a 2D spin lattice). The TN is partitioned into N sub-networks, drawn here with $N = 4$. In an inner loop, for each sub-network we follow the variational procedure outlined by Lin et. al [9] and optimize gates $U(\theta_N)$ for an efficient circuit representation of each sub-network. Following this optimization, in the outer loop we compute entanglement measures (e.g., von Neumann entropy)

Fig. 2. Schematic of the adaptive circuit knitting method. In the inner loop, a variational optimizer finds circuit parameters for partitions of a quantum system (based on a tensor network) in parallel. In the outer loop, an adaptive procedure finds cuts which minimize entanglement between partitions. After the best cuts are found, observables are reconstructed via circuit knitting.

and construct an entropy heatmap among the qubits. Although this heatmap is partial (we do not have entropy measures at the cuts between partitions), we use the information available and update cuts to locations with low entanglement. With new cuts on the following iterations, the blind spots are revealed. The adaptive outer loop exits when entanglement between partitions is minimized. The inner loop can be parallelized since each sub-network is independent, and both the inner and outer loop can be executed on classical HPC.

Once optimal partitions have been found, a measured observable can be reconstructed from the sub-circuits via circuit knitting [5]. As we demonstrate in the following section, cutting gates at locations of minimal entanglement can drastically lower the classical overhead of circuit knitting.

III. RESULTS FOR QUANTUM SPIN CHAINS

Simulating quantum systems for materials science or quantum chemistry is perhaps the most promising application for quantum computers. Spin-lattice systems are well-studied in materials science, and despite their simplicity can exhibit complex quantum phenomena that are difficult to simulate classically [10], [11]. As a prototype system, we apply our adaptive circuit knitting method to simulating the non-equilibrium dynamics of a strongly-disordered spin chain evolving under an Ising model with transverse and longitudinal fields given by the Hamiltonian $H = -\sum_{i=1}^{N-1} J_{i,i+1} \sigma_i^z \sigma_{i+1}^z - \sum_{i=1}^N g_i \sigma_i^x - \sum_{i=1}^N h_i \sigma_i^z$, where σ^z and σ^x are the Pauli Z and X matrices, respectively, i indexes lattice site, and J_s , g_s , and h_s are real-valued parameters. We study strongly-disordered systems (where parameters are varied at each lattice site) because they are important for understanding exotic states of matter, they can be difficult to study, and because they lead to many-body localization effects which we suspect can be exploited for more efficient simulation.

Figure 3 provides a summary of the results for an ensemble of 100 20-qubit spin chains, each time-evolving under a Hamiltonian with different parameters chosen randomly from a uniform distribution on $[-1, 1]$ (excluding 0). For each spin chain, circuit optimization was carried out at eight timesteps

throughout the dynamics. We partition each system into two sub-circuits and compare the overhead cost of circuit knitting for a naive cut in the middle of the chain (a 'load-balanced' choice) vs. a cut recommended by the entropy heatmap from the adaptive algorithm. Fig. 3a gives a schematic for a single instance. Fig. 3b shows the distribution of overheads for reconstructing a magnetization observable via circuit knitting for the adaptive and naive cuts. Both cuts achieve similar accuracy in the observable, but in most cases the adaptive cut results in a much lower overhead—the green distribution is clearly shifted to the left. On a case-by-case basis, the median reduction in cost was 12x, while the 75th and 95th percentiles were 55x and 516x, respectively. While not shown in this figure, the gap between adaptive and load-balanced baseline widens during the later timesteps, indicating that for longer simulations the benefits of adaptive circuit knitting will increase.

Fig. 3. (a) Example of a 20-qubit spin chain where the adaptive cut is chosen at the minimum entanglement entropy. (b) Histogram of sampling overheads resulting from adaptive and load-balanced baseline cuts for an ensemble of 20-qubit strongly-disordered spin chains. Calculations performed using quantum circuit simulators parallelized with mpi4py running on classical HPC (AMD CPUs across several nodes).

IV. SUMMARY AND OUTLOOK

We presented adaptive circuit knitting, a method for efficiently partitioning quantum circuits to enable distributed, high-performance quantum computing. We applied the method to circuits simulating the non-equilibrium dynamics of strongly-disordered quantum spin chains, and found it was common to see improvements in overhead of one to two orders of magnitude over the baseline load-balanced cut. Future work will include investigating fast entanglement measures, exploring more sophisticated convergence criteria, and studying 2D systems with higher order TN techniques, as 2D systems are where many classical methods fail and quantum computers could likely provide the largest advantage.

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